

COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The article examines the importance and advantages of innovations in small business activities. Statistical indicators of innovative activities of small business entities were analyzed.

Key words: small business, innovation, innovative activity, competitive advantage.

Support of small business and private entrepreneurship provides not only economic goals related to the continuous development of the economy, correction of economic relations, development of competition and filling of the consumer market.

In order to make small business and private entrepreneurship more stable in our country, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Additional measures to fundamentally improve the system of organizing work on the protection of private property and strengthening the guarantees of the rights of owners, supporting entrepreneurial initiatives, as well as the Decree No. PF-5780 dated August 13, 2019 on expanding the opportunities of business entities to use financial resources and production infrastructure and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Small business under the Ministry of Economy and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan and on the organization of the activity of the entrepreneurship development agency" dated August 13, 2019 PQ-4417 was adopted. Competition is a conflict of economic interests of market entities, which means a struggle between them for higher profits and greater productivity.[1]

Competition — struggle between independent producers (enterprises) to produce goods under favorable conditions and sell them at a profitable price, to strengthen their position in the economy as a whole. Competition is a multifaceted economic phenomenon that represents complex relations between all market entities. Competition between suppliers of resources takes place to sell their economic resources (capital, land, labor) at a higher price. Competition between producers and suppliers of resources is clearly manifested in the conditions of developed market relations and fully liberalized economy.

Competition also occurs among consumers, focused on buying goods at convenient and low prices, that is, the buyer tries to get more benefits for each unit of money spent, fights to buy cheap and high-quality goods as quickly as possible. In competition, there is a struggle among producers to get more profit for the costs incurred, and as a result of the pursuit of this profit, there are outlets for goods, that is, favorable markets, sources of cheap raw materials, energy, and cheap labor. Competition is based on separation and independence of producers as owners of property, conflict of interests.

Because every property owner has his own interest, and they strive to achieve this interest. The activity of the owner of the property in the production of goods and in all other areas will be subordinated to this interest. Another condition for the existence of competition is the

presence of commodity-money relations, a certain level of developed market system. Therefore, the main field of competition is the market.

The introduction of new technology, the rapid adoption of on-demand product types, the availability of skilled labor and the use of modern marketing services become a condition for winning the competition. Monopoly is the opposite of Competition because it gives monopoly to the producer of a good and leaves no room for competition. Competition is also divided into honest and honorable competition in terms of choosing the way to fight.

In the action strategy for the development of our country for the period of 2017-2021, small business has set a wide range of tasks. In order to effectively solve these tasks, great importance is attached to innovative activities in the management of small business entities. In order to implement active entrepreneurship, there must be innovative entrepreneurship. Innovative activity should form the essence of entrepreneurial activity. In order to have an honorable name, any person should work on himself, search for news, create, search. An entrepreneur who wants to survive and survive in the fierce competition in the market economy must be innovative and implement innovative management. It is a vital necessity. Innovation is a law of competition, a characteristic feature of market economy, without which the market system will never develop.[3]

Factors of active entrepreneurship. We believe that it is of great importance for small business entities with various potentials to pay special attention to the following in determining their innovation potential, in order to implement active entrepreneurship and intensively apply innovative activities:

1. Wide use of incentives
2. Use of opportunities
3. Overcoming various restrictions and obstacles

A small business owner is constantly looking for ways to make a profit. For this, it tries to produce a quality, competitive or completely new type of product. For this, he improves his technology, introduces innovations, that is, he searches for, finds and applies innovations in his enterprise. All these actions require certain costs.

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At the same time, the product brought to the market may not be well received in the market, having incurred large costs. If it is not sold in sufficient quantities, the costs incurred may not be covered. Some features of the product may not have been adequately considered. Therefore, any entrepreneur should think many times and make calculations in order to implement any new work, innovation.[5]

Together with this, there is a force that drives an entrepreneur to take innovative risks. It is a competitive force in the market. Due to the large number of product manufacturers in the market, there is a strong competition between them. Every manufacturer tries to sell more products. Anyone who slows down the action, indulges in complacency, can lose the competition. Such a risk is a constant companion of any entrepreneur. Therefore, it will be the driving force for the entrepreneur's innovative activity. That's what drives innovation.

In small business entities, it is also necessary to have certain opportunities to work on an innovative project. It should be the result of some invented innovation or scientific and technical activity, or can buy a ready license from the foreign market, conduct patent research. If there is a problem, scientists and researchers work on this problem and try to find a solution.

Therefore, an entrepreneur should convey his problems to research institutions. All such work requires the entrepreneur to have funds. There should also be funds for the introduction of the created innovation. Small business entities lack funding to implement major innovations.

Therefore, small business entities can join together. This is the only way to overcome such limitations. As a result, large business entities are formed.

Small business provides about 60% of the country's gross domestic product, one third of the volume of industrial products, 98% of agricultural products, and half of investments. In many regions, 70-90 percent of exports go to small businesses.

Small business and private entrepreneurship play a fundamental role in ensuring the country's economic growth, filling the consumer market with goods and services, creating new jobs, and improving the standard of living of the population. At the same time, small business entities and their activities in the implementation of innovative activities are important in the formation of innovative economy in our country. In the conditions of the knowledge economy, innovation has become a necessary factor of small business activity. Innovation plays an important role in the survival of enterprises in the market and is usually expressed through the commercialization of new knowledge and ideas. Innovation is a necessary factor for the productivity and growth of enterprises.

Schumpeter sees the entrepreneur as the driving force of development. "The main result of innovation is profit, which motivates the innovator to continuously create innovations that lead to the development of society," he suggests. In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 24, 2020 "On Innovative Activity" No. O'RQ-630, the term innovation is included in civil circulation or used for personal needs, the use of which in practice ensures the achievement of great socio-economic results. It is explained as development. From the perspective of SMEs, innovations are usually new products or processes that meet customer needs in a more unique and profitable way than existing products.[2]

Quick adaptability to market changes, the wide range of opportunities for self-expression of employees, the opportunities and benefits created for small business entities expand the opportunities of representatives of this sector to engage in innovative activities. The implementation of innovative activities by small businesses allows the following - to increase labor productivity; - Cost reduction; - Having competitive advantages; - Increase market share or strengthen existing market share; - Increasing profitability indicators; - Rational use of available material and labor resources; - Increasing the export potential and others. The

diagram below shows the indicators of innovative activity of small business entities, in which the ratio of the level of innovative activity of small business to the total number of small business entities of small enterprises and micro-firms that produced innovative products, works, services on their own calculated through.

According to statistical data, in 2021, the number of small business entities that produced innovative products, works, and services on their own, when analyzed by region, the leading three are Tashkent city (1137), Tashkent (545) and Navoi regions (391) took place. The lowest indicators were observed in Jizzakh (710) and Khorezm (69) regions, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (43). The main reasons for achieving high results of Tashkent city and Tashkent region in many other indicators of the innovative activity of small business entities are, first of all, the large number of small business entities in the region, the high level of intellectual potential. we can estimate that it is the dense location of the lim institutions, the permanent aspiration of qualified specialists and personnel to the center and, of course, the better formation of the innovative infrastructure compared to other regions. Key indicators of small business innovative activity, in %.

From the data of the diagram, we can see that from 2016 to 2020, the innovative activity of small business entities has increased. However, in 2021, the indicator of innovative activity decreased by almost 2 times compared to 2020 and amounted to 0.84%. The share of the volume of innovative products, works, and services produced by small business entities in the total revenue from the sale of products, works, and services reached 4.98% in 2020, and by 2021 it was 2.55%. almost doubled in one year.

The dynamics of decrease was also observed in the share of expenditures made by small business entities on technological, marketing, and organizational innovations in the net income from the sale of total products (goods, works, and services). In 2016, expenditures on technological, marketing, and organizational innovations amounted to 211.4 billion. amounted to 1165.7 billion soums by 2021. reached soums. [4]

The share of these expenses in the total net income from the sale of products, work, and services has not changed much. The reason for these low indicators can be explained by the low propensity of small business entities to innovations, the insufficient formation of innovative infrastructure, the existence of financial barriers, as well as the insufficient human capital of entrepreneurs and employees in this field.

In short, innovation is an integral part of small business operations. In our country, the innovative activity of small business entities is low. However, the reforms that are being implemented to create an innovative economy will expand the scope of innovative activities of small business entities. After all, as a result of innovations and innovative activities, enterprises are provided with high profits, have a competitive advantage, and manage to maintain their viability for a long time.

References:

1. E. Cefis, O. Marsili. The role of innovation in firms' survival. Research policy, 35 (2006), pp. 626-641.
2. P. Ganotakis. Founders' human capital and the performance of UK new technology based firms. Small business economics, 39 (2012), pp. 495-515.
3. Y. Schumpeter. Theory of economic development. M.:Ekonomika, 1995g.-540 st.

4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 24, 2020 "On Innovative Activities" ORQ-630. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4910391>)
5. O'Regan, N., Ghobadian, A. Perceptions of generic strategies of small business and medium sized engineering and electronics manufacturers in the UK. Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management, 17(5), 603-620

